

Vanuatu Sand Drawing Terminology Questionnaire

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1. Introduction

Sand drawing is a cultural practice found only in the central islands of Vanuatu where geometric patterns are drawn on the ground with a finger. Often, gridlines are drawn first and then the finger traces a continuous line through the corners of the gridlines to reveal an image. These images depict different entities, such as birds, mammals, fruit, nuts, root crops, but also abstract communicative messages, ritual practices and traditional narratives.

Sand drawing is still practiced across the Vanuatu archipelago but it is an under documented cultural practice, despite it being a UNESCO Intangible Cultural Heritage (Zagala 2004). Documenting current sand drawing practice in different language communities is essential to understanding how productive and widespread the practice is. Further research will also shed light on how this practice has been transmitted intergenerationally and how it has been diffused throughout the archipelago.

Current data on sand drawing is limited to collections from only a few language communities. Sand drawing is practiced in Epi, Malakula, Ambrym, Paama, Pentecost, Maewo, Ambae and potentially in parts of Santo. This area encompasses over 60 languages and to date only limited data from around a dozen or so languages has been collected.

There are different layers to the practice that are essential to a full documentation:

- The drawings
- The names of the drawings
- The narratives associated with the drawings
- The terminology for the different sub-movements and parts of the drawings
- Contextual discussions of the practice itself, such as information on its cultural importance, how it is traded and passed on intergenerationally, and where different designs originated, etc.

The data collected from this questionnaire will be used to shed light on how sand drawing has been diffused throughout central Vanuatu by comparing the drawings, names, narratives and associated terminology. I plan to update this questionnaire as more data is collected and analysed. I will be very appreciative of any thoughts and suggestions, and of course the data that results from using the questionnaire.

Figure 1: *Fwel ta Unu* ‘the bald man from Wunu’. Photo of sand drawing performed by John Taso of Ranvetlam village, North Ambrym. Line drawings depicting gridlines and finished drawing with each movement numbered.¹
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2. The Drawings and their names

Each language community will potentially have dozens of different drawings, with expert practitioners able to create new designs. Drawings can also be unique and known by only one practitioner, or can be known by different practitioners in a particular language

¹ Note a small mistake in the numbering - movement 48 joins into movement 50.

community. The same drawing can also be found across different language communities in Vanuatu.

Variations on the same drawing exist in the same language community, and so it is worthwhile recording the same drawing from different practitioners. Variations could be embellishments, where additional movements distinguish between drawings. Variations could also be different starting nodes of the gridlines, or different starting directions.

Each drawing will have a name associated with it. There may be variation in the name in different areas for the same drawing – either within the same linguistic community or across different language communities. The same or similar drawings in two different language communities can depict different entities and therefore will have different names. Record the name in the vernacular language and provide word glosses and translation.

3. Narratives

Some sand drawings depict aspects of traditional narratives or ecological knowledge, which should be recorded along with the drawing. Preferably, record in the vernacular language, transcribe and provide word glosses and translations. Though if not possible, record in both the vernacular and Bislama and transcribe and translate the Bislama version. This will aid future fine-grained analysis.

Sand drawings have layered meanings, depending upon both the knowledge of the practitioner and on who the audience is. There will be a profane meaning and there may also be customary knowledge associated with the drawing that only certain types of audience members will have an understanding of – for example, initiates of the graded *nimangki* society. Only record what the practitioner allows you to, ensuring they have given informed consent for how the recording will be used later.

Similar to the names of the sand drawings, different narratives could be associated with the same drawing either within or across language boundaries. It is best to record versions from different practitioners to ensure documentation of all variations. Furthermore, some practitioners may recount additional aspects of the narrative or knowledge associated with the drawing that others practitioners do not know.

4. The Terminology for the Movements

There is a set of specialised vocabulary that is associated with the different parts and movements of the drawings. The terminology is used as both an *aide memoire* for the practitioner and for teaching others in how to correctly execute the drawing. The terminology can be specific to the domain of sand drawing, but more often the terms used are metaphorical extensions of existing basic vocabulary.

A fuller overview of the terminology collected so far from several languages can be found in Franjeh (2026). The questionnaire in section 6 can be used to help elicit the terminology associated with different sand drawing movements.

5. Recording and Collecting Data

The best way to document sand drawing and its associated terminology is through focussed video recordings and interviews with practitioners. Ideally record with an audience who are learning the art form or with other practitioners as this will lead to further discussion and often the narration of the drawing using the technical vocabulary.

I find mounting a video camera on a tripod useful to capture the drawing from above. Often the practitioners offer to put a layer of ash on the ground first – I find the contrast useful for recording the drawings. After a few drawings it is best to sweep the ash away and add a new layer. Take photos as well – of the gridlines and of the final drawing from the different perspectives.

If you have time, creating line drawings, either by hand or on the computer, is useful to show starting points and directions of the movements – see figure 1.

6. Terminology Questionnaire

In the following pages I present images of each of the movements that have been found to have terminology associated with them so far. I avoid naming each movement for three reasons. First, there is variation across languages in the terminology used and I do not want to give preference to a particular language. Second, there can be variation in terminological conventions between different practitioners from the same language community. Third, naming the terms in this document could lead to practitioners offering a calque/translation.

Not every movement may have a term associated with it and practitioners may not know the terms for all the movements if a term does exist. It is best to not force a practitioner to name a term if they are unsure. Ideally work with different practitioners to get a fuller inventory of terms.

When describing the term, it is really helpful to get examples sentences of use for all senses of the term, not just the specialised sand drawing sense. For example, terms may be used in other domains such as house building, animal husbandry, horticulture etc.

There may be specific lexical items associated with a movement, or the practitioner may give a larger sentence-level description of the movement.

6.1.

There can be multiple terms for the gridlines:

- A generic term for the gridlines (both horizontal and vertical)
- A specific term for the vertical gridlines
- A specific term for the horizontal gridlines
- A term for the nodes / intersection between two gridlines
- A term for the spaces between the gridlines
- There may also be terms for different types of grids, rather than just the lattice type shown below, such as dots/points that the continuous line of the drawing moves around

6.2.

An arc between two adjacent nodes.

6.3

A series of alternating arcs.

6.4.

A line intersecting two diagonally opposite nodes

6.5.

A small loop that often goes beyond the confines of the grid that starts and ends on the same node but in the opposite direction

6.6.

A series of loops and arcs

6.7

A series of four arcs that make up a circle

6.8

There may be terms for the series of four arcs that make up a circle depending on the starting direction of the movement stemming from the initial diagonal line: (a) clockwise or (b) anticlockwise. There may be different terms based on the viewing perspective of the practitioner – try rotating the images.

(a) Clockwise

(b) Anticlockwise

6.9

A diagonal line followed by three arcs of a circle followed by a further diagonal line.

6.10

A diagonal line followed by three arcs in the reverse direction, followed by a final diagonal line. This movement goes beyond the confines of the grid.

6.11

This movement starts with a diagonal line that goes beyond the confines of the grid, before arcing and drawing three quarters of a circle and meeting back at where the diagonal intersected with the grid.

6.12

Two of the movements detailed in 6.11 with a small loop in between. In some languages this combination has a specific term. In others there is no specific term, but can be described using a larger sentence combining the term for 6.11 and 6.5.

6.13

Two short diagonal lines that cross over adjacent nodes.

6.14

A complex movement made up of an arc, three small loops that go beyond the confines of the grid, followed by a further arc.

6.15

A large loop that goes beyond the confines of the grid and covers the movement described in 6.14.

6.16

Another movement that covers the movement described in 6.14. some languages may use the same term as 6.15. There may be an alternative name for this movement, or it could be described using a combination of the term used in 6.15 and in 6.5.

6.17

A large loop that goes beyond the confines of the grid

6.18

A large loop that goes beyond the confines of the grid. Note the direction of the initial and final arc – distinguishing this movement from 6.17.

6.19

A finishing flourish – this can be a series of up to four small loop movements (c.f. 6.5) that brings the direction of the final line of the drawing back to the same direction as the initial starting direction of the drawing.

6.20

A list of terms that should also be investigated and collected:

- The name for sand drawing in general.
- The starting point of the drawing
- The finishing point of the drawing
- Iconic parts of the drawing, such as body parts or parts of a plant.
- Smaller movements can be combined into a larger repetitive sequence which may have a name in the language (e.g., see how a series of arcs can make up the sequences shown in 6.3 and 6.7)
- Any different movements that you see – particularly movements that go beyond the confines of the grid – these movements are often more free and can take on different forms and may have names associated with them

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References

- Franjeh, Michael. 2026. The language of sand drawing: tracing its history through shared terminology and metaphors. *Journal de la Société des Océanistes*, 162.
- Zagala, Stephen, 2004. Vanuatu Sand Drawing. *Museum International*, 56(1-2), 32-35.